

Final Program

August 26-29, 2024 – New Brunswick

37TH International Symposium
for the Society of Core Analysts

From the 2024 President

Dear Colleagues and Friends,

On behalf of the Society and Board of Directors, it is my great pleasure to welcome you to the 37th International Symposium of the Society of Core Analysis (SCA), in Fredericton, New Brunswick, Canada, August 25-30, 2024.

Addressing the escalating impact of climate change while ensuring global energy security presents both a significant challenge and a good opportunity for professionals in our society. Hydrocarbon production from various subsurface formations, including unconventional source rock reservoir, remains crucial to meet the increasing global energy demand driven by population growth and rising living standards. Various approaches proposed and developed for energy transition to mitigate climate change also involves working with subsurface formations, such as geological carbon sequestration, geothermal extraction, and hydrogen geological storage and in situ production. Our society plays a vital role in providing clear insights and recommendations on the fluids, the rocks, and the fluids movement in the rocks for all these subsurface formations. I am confident our community can and will address all the challenges by leveraging existing technology and developing innovative new methods and tools. Notably, the application of artificial intelligence (AI) and deep learning represent a new technology area in core analysis.

The SCA symposium remains a pivotal annual event for the core analysis community. Our participants represent a balanced mix of academics and industry professionals (approximately 50% each), a unique blend rarely seen in other societies. The symposium's intimate size and single-session format allow easy and sufficient interactions for attendees to exchange ideas on established and/or emerging technologies. In addition, a diverse range of exhibitions at the symposium will showcase novel equipment, methods, and software.

To all those involved in making this event possible, I extend my deepest gratitude. Special recognition goes to the VP Technology, Ryan Armstrong, and the technical committee for their diligent review process and development of the technical program. The VP Arrangement, Jenny Cain, has meticulously organized the venue, accommodations, and social program. The support of the SCA Executive Director, Melanie Young, ensures the symposium's smooth execution. Lastly, I greatly appreciate all participants who contribute to the symposium through papers, presentations, and exhibitions.

With confidence, I anticipate another outstanding symposium this year, filled with enriching discussions and valuable networking opportunities. I eagerly look forward to meeting you all in Fredericton, Canada!

JinHong Chen
SCA President

From the 2024 VP Arrangements

Dear Colleagues and Guests,

As we approach the much-anticipated 2024 SCA Annual Symposium in Fredericton, New Brunswick, I am delighted to extend a warm welcome to each of you. It is an honor to host this prestigious event in a city renowned for its charm, hospitality, and vibrant culture.

Fredericton, with its picturesque landscapes and welcoming atmosphere, offers a unique backdrop for our gathering. The city's scenic downtown area is home to an array of quaint shops, inviting cafes, and historic landmarks, including the iconic Legislative Assembly Building and the stunning Christ Church Cathedral. Fredericton is also known for its lush green spaces and well-maintained parks, offering a serene environment to enjoy outdoor activities. Friendly and welcoming, Fredericton embodies the warmth of maritime hospitality, offering a blend of small-town charm and urban convenience. Whether you're strolling along the riverfront, exploring its historic sites, or immersing yourself in local culture, Fredericton provides a memorable experience for all who visit.

Our team has been working diligently to ensure that every aspect of the conference is meticulously arranged to provide you with a seamless and enriching experience. From the short course and technical sessions to the networking opportunities and social events, we have strived to create an environment that fosters both professional growth and meaningful connections.

We are confident that the sessions and discussions planned will spark innovative ideas and foster valuable collaborations. Your participation is crucial to the success of this conference, and we are excited to share this journey with you.

We extend our deepest gratitude to our generous sponsors and dedicated vendors for their invaluable support. Our heartfelt thanks also go to the authors, technical committee members, and volunteers whose collective efforts have made this event a resounding success and a truly memorable experience.

Thank you for your commitment and enthusiasm. We look forward to the opportunity to reconnect with each and every participant and to an exceptional conference experience.

Warm regards,

Jenny Cain
VP of Arrangements

From the 2024 VP Technology

Dear Colleagues and Friends,

Welcome to the 2024 SCA International Symposium in Fredericton, New Brunswick, Canada!

We are thrilled to gather for the 37th annual SCA Symposium, focusing this year on advancing our knowledge in “Digital Core Analysis: Pore-Scale Imaging, Modelling, and Deep Learning.” This year, we received 81 abstracts. I extend my gratitude to all the authors who submitted their work. Whether your abstract was accepted or not, your contributions are invaluable to the ongoing success of our society and annual symposium.

After a meticulous review process, we have scheduled 34 oral presentations and 26 posters. I am grateful to the entire technical committee for their dedication, attention to detail, and efforts to enhance every paper’s quality. Thank you to all authors and reviewers for embodying the technical excellence that the SCA stands for.

Our short course this year will cover “Digital Core Analysis,” kicking off on the morning of August 26. Special thanks to Maša Prodanović, Peyman Mostaghimi, Lesley James, and Olivier Lopez for preparing this insightful course. I trust it will be both engaging and educational for our community.

A heartfelt thank you to our SCA Executive Director, Melanie Young, whose tireless efforts have been instrumental in organizing this year’s program.

I look forward to seeing you in Fredericton and to the vibrant exchange of ideas that will undoubtedly propel our field forward.

Warm regards,

Ryan T. Armstrong
SCA VP of Technology

Current SCA Board

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2024 Technical Committee

The SCA Technical Committee is the backbone of the Society of Core Analysts. Its members rank and evaluate the submitted abstracts and the technical quality of the manuscripts. In the review of each individual manuscript and in-depth discussions with the authors, many hours are spent until a manuscript is accepted. In many cases, the interaction between authors and TC members leads to a higher quality of individual manuscripts. As a result, the annual SCA symposia are packed with high-quality presentations. For this, sincere acknowledgement go to this year's Technical Committee members:

Adam Moss	JinHong Chen	Stefano Pruno
Arjen Cense	John Mills	Steffen Berg
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Benjamin Nicot	Jos Maas	Will Richardson
Benjamin Anger	Josephina Schembre-McCabe	Xiaolong Yin
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Cyril CAUBIT	Matthias Halisch	Saman Aryana
David Potter	Mike Dick	Thomas Ramstad
Einar Ebeltoft	Mike Spearing	Ying Gao
Fabrice Pairoys	Mohamed Regaieg	Ying Da Wang
Falah Koronfol	Moustafa Dernaika	Lesley James
Felix Feldmann	Muhammad Rehan Hashmet	Kunning Tang
Franck Nono	Olga Vizika	Naif Alqahtani
Gerald Hamon	Olivier Lopez	Jianchao Cal
Harry Xie	Omid Karoussi	Qinhong Hu
Hassan Mahani	Patrick Egermann	Michael Rauschhuber
Hendrik Rohler	Roland Lenormand	Reza Askarinezhad
Holger Ott	Ryan Armstrong	
Hyung Kwak	Shannon Eichmann	
Issa Abu Shiekah	Shouxiang Mark Ma	
James Howard	Souhail Youssef	
James Funk	Stacey Althaus	

Technical Achievement Darcy Award Recipient

Dr Xudong Jing (FEI, FRSC, CEng), Visiting Professor in Engineering,
Imperial College London

Dr. Xudong Jing has over 30 years of international experience gained with Imperial College London, Shell and ADNOC. He held technical and leadership roles in oil and gas development, improved and enhanced recovery (IOR/EOR), unconventional oil and gas and carbon capture, utilisation and storage (CCUS).

Dr. Jing made a strong and lasting impact in the development and application of enhanced oil recovery technologies focusing on energy-efficient processes. He has been an unwavering champion of low-carbon development and played an important role in initiating solar energy for steam generation and expanding polymer flooding to challenging reservoir conditions both of which have increased recovery and reduced GHG emissions. He led team efforts to develop polymer flooding at commercial scales that added significant recoverable volumes while significantly reducing associated GHG emission per unit volume produced. He received the Distinguished Membership Award by the Society of Petroleum Engineers (SPE) in 2022 for his pioneering work in using reservoir characterization to address full field polymer EOR implementation challenges.

He made important contributions in the characterization, modelling and recovery of heterogeneous carbonate reservoirs. He and his co-authors published seminal papers that set the standard for the characterization and modelling of carbonate reservoirs and improved the predictions of production performance under waterflooding. He was also co-author on hybrid EOR technologies for heterogeneous carbonate reservoirs including CO₂, water or polymer injections, adding additional resource volumes at reduced unit technical costs. He has co-authored over 100 papers with focus on core analysis and flow in porous media and two books including “The Imperial College Lectures in Petroleum Engineering – Drilling and Reservoir Appraisal” published in 2018 that focused on the science and practice of core analysis and related field applications.

Dr. Jing has served on the executive and technical committees of numerous international learned societies (SCA, SPE, EAGE, SEG). He is a Fellow of the Energy Institute (FEI), a Fellow of Royal Society of Chemistry (FRSC), a Chartered Engineer

(CEng) and a Distinguished Member of the Society of Petroleum Engineers. Since becoming a SCA member in 1988, He has actively participated in and contributed to SCA activities and publications including serving as SCA President (2002-2003), SCA VP Technology (2000- 2001) and winning the 2003 SCA Best Paper Award. Dr. Jing holds a BSc from China University of Petroleum and PhD from Imperial College London.

The Venue

The Fredericton Convention Centre (FCC) is located on “Canada’s Greatest Street” as Queen Street was named in April 2012. The centre is chic and stylish, filled with natural light, highlighting local art along the walls of the foyer and reception areas. With more than 36,000 square feet of flexible meeting space, FCC is the best location for your next meeting, convention or conference on the east coast of Canada!

The FCC is located in the heart of downtown Fredericton, across the street from the Saint John River (Wolastoq) and more than 100km of walking and biking trails. Surrounded by ethnic and local restaurants, unique shopping and world renowned art galleries such as the Beaverbrook Art Gallery, delegates attending events at FCC will have a fantastic Maritime experience!

Short Courses – Monday 26th, 8:30 a.m. – 12:30 p.m.

Short Workshop: Digital Core Analysis: Pore-Scale Imaging, Modelling, and Deep Learning.

A special thanks to the presenters who helped put this short workshop together; Masha Prodanovic, Peyman Mostaghimi, Lesley James, Olivier Lopez, and Ryan Armstrong.

Coffee and tea will be available during breaks. Lunch will be provided to attendees.

Short Course is Kindly Sponsored by:

Opening Reception – Monday 26th, 5:30p.m. - 8:30 p.m.

The Opening “Icebreaker” Reception will be held in the Exhibitor Hall. Snacks and drinks will be served to foster a relaxed atmosphere to meet and greet both old and new colleagues.

Dress Code: Business casual

Kindly Sponsored by: Chevron

Technical Sessions – Monday 26th, Tuesday 27^h, Wednesday 28th and Thursday 29th, 8:00 a.m. - 5 p.m.

(With the exception for start at 1:30 p.m. on Monday).

Oral presentations: The Symposium will offer 34 oral presentations, 20 minute presentations followed by 10 minutes for discussion.

Poster sessions: The symposium will offer 28 posters, distributed in three poster sessions.

Young Professionals Event – Tuesday 27th, 5:30-9:00 p.m.

Quillis Waterpark

Come on out and enjoy our very own inflatable waterpark followed by dinner.

Bring your swimsuit and towels!

Kindly Sponsored by:

Awards Gala Dinner – Wednesday 28th, 6:30 - 9:30 pm

The gala dinner will be held at the Picaroons Roundhouse Brewing Company.

This will be a fun filled evening of BBQ food, local craft brews, lawn games, a live band and more.

Dress code: Business Casual.

Gala Dinner is Kindly Sponsored by: iRock Technologies and Chevron

Optional Field Trip – Friday August 30th, 6:30 a.m.- 6:00 p.m.

Optional Friday Field Trip

Kayaking Hopewell Rocks

Leave the Fredericton Convention Center at 6:30 am on Friday, August 30th

Please ensure you have appropriate footwear and a change of clothes.

- Transportation and bagged lunch provided.
- Arrival to Hopewell Rocks: 9:00 am
- Kayak around the Rock Formations during hide tide – 2 Hours
- Lunch
- Walk the Ocean floor during low tide
- Departure to Convention Center at 3:30 pm

Kindly Sponsored by:

Publication of Proceedings

The proceedings are prepared in online format and login details will be given at the Symposium to all registered participants.

www.SCAweb.org

The SCA has decided to no longer carry printed copies of the proceedings.

Exhibition Hours

Monday: 8:30 a.m. – 5:30 p.m.	*Exhibition Build-up starts at 8:30am
Tuesday: 8:30 a.m. – 5:00 p.m.	
Wednesday: 8:00 a.m. – 5:00 p.m.	
Thursday: 8:00 a.m. – 5:00 p.m	*Exhibition Break-down can start after the afternoon break and complete by 5pm.

Exhibitor

AMETEK Chandler Engineering – AMETEK Chandler Engineering is at the forefront of decarbonization of existing industries, and the leader of environmental solutions to mitigate well integrity problems. Chandler Engineering has the expertise in the design and implementation of Core Flow Systems for Reservoir Analysis, Carbon Utilization and Storage (CUS), and Well Integrity Instruments used to Responsibly Source Oil and Gas (RSG), Corrosion and Scale Testing, Custom Engineered Solutions including Pilot Plants and PVT systems, and of course, our line of Quizix precision pump products. This year, Chandler Engineering celebrates 75 years of providing HPHT measurement solutions to the O&G industry. We look forward to working with you on your instrumentation requirements for not only today's challenges, but for the next 75 years.

Core Technical Services - CTS is a Subsurface Analysis and Visualisation Specialist - We have a global presence in the Core digitisation market, together with our trusted partners and clients across the globe we have already begun the digital transformation. Core Technical Services has a great reputation for providing core analysis services and products worldwide. What sets us apart from the rest is our ability to customize our offering to customers' needs, as well as our fantastic team of specialists.

Our strength lies not only within our internal team, but also with our extensive network of associate subject matter experts (SMEs) in a wide range of disciplines, including reservoir engineering, geomechanics, coring, well planning, and much more. If you need a core-related skill we don't have in-house, we can source it.

Daedalus Innovations - Daedalus Innovations offers cutting edge tools to utilize high pressure in NMR based studies. High active volume coupled with high pressure tolerance opens a host of applications in areas as diverse as petroleum chemistry, structural biology and quantum computing. The high RF permeability of the vessel material allows for the full suite of modern NMR spectroscopy techniques to be applied while safely under pressure. Daedalus Innovations is the only provider of seamlessly integrated pressure generation and robust large active volume high resolution NMR cells rated to operation at pressures as high as 3,000 bar. We are also a leader in the development of the overburden rock core cells for NMR and MRI for comprehensive reservoir analysis such as EOR or carbon storage applications. We are constantly innovating and expanding our product base to work with instrumentation from a host of vendors and a range of core sizes needed to meet today's research needs. Visit us at www.daedalusinnovations.com to see how we might help in your research efforts.

DCI Corporation - DCI offers innovative solutions to your core testing requirements. From turnkey systems to system components we can help you with your laboratory needs. DCI designs and manufactures both custom and standard core holders, accumulators, syringe pumps, acoustic separators, core flood systems, electrical resistivity systems, rock mechanics systems and much more. Stop by our booth to see how DCI can help you make better measurements on core properties.

Green Imaging Technologies, Inc – Green Imaging Technologies is the industry leader in NMR rock core analysis. Our software is the backbone of the Oxford GeoSpec line of NMR Rock Core Analyzers, which are used by all major oil producers, oil service companies and the most active research institutes worldwide. Our customers have access to exclusive, patented measurements including NMR capillary pressure and quantitative saturation profiles. Our team of experts are focused on rock core analysis, and as such have developed relationships with the most respected researchers and experts in the NMR rock core analysis field. We are always looking for new NMR applications and look forward to talking to current and potential NMR users about how NMR can help them solve their reservoir puzzles.

HOT Microfluidics GmbH - Based in Goslar at the Energy Research Centre of Lower Saxony (Germany), HOT Microfluidics focuses on experiments with hydrogen, carbon dioxide, and gas mixtures in compliance with the highest HSE standards. As a leading High-Pressure, high-temperature (HPHT) technology provider for PVT, IOR/EOR, and New Energy applications, HOT Microfluidics helps Energy companies and research organisations globally speed up lab routines at a significantly reduced cost. (www.fluidicslab.com)

Math2Market GmbH - Math2Market develops GeoDict, a comprehensive simulation software solution that includes software, support, project work, user training, and custom developments and extensions. The GeoDict package specifically designed for Digital Rock Physics and Digital Core Analysis (DRP-DCA) combines with imaging capabilities, to perform these workflows accurately, completely, digitally, and in-house. It boasts exceptionally fast runtimes, the ability to handle extremely large datasets, and low hardware requirements or cloud usage. Recently added features include the simulation of two-phase flow with the entire hysteresis cycle and the digital analysis of rocks for CO₂ sequestration techniques and storage mechanisms.

Oxford Instruments - Oxford Instruments plc is a leading provider of high technology products and services to the world's leading industrial companies and scientific research communities.

Our core purpose is to enable a greener, healthier, more connected advanced society. We are proud to be recognized as the leaders in what we do and for the difference we make in the world.

Petricore – Petricore offers an extensive suite of Rock Lab Services: Routine Core Analysis, Special Core Analysis (SCAL), and Digital Rock Analysis, in addition to Wellsite Services. Committed to excellence, with specialized teams in Mexico, USA, and Norway, our priority is quality and customer care. We provide customized services in close collaboration with clients. Our experts are always keen to assist.

Prores AS - Sendra SaaS is at the forefront of transforming Special Core Analysis (SCAL) multiphase flow simulation and data utilization within subsurface digitalization and automation. Our cloud-native solution leverages an extensive SCAL database to improve uncertainty estimation and generate reliable capillary pressure and relative permeability curves. By utilizing this comprehensive database, Sendra SaaS supports full-field applications without requiring new core samples, thus significantly reducing the need for additional cores. Incorporating advanced AI technology, our platform minimizes the necessity for further experiments, saving time and resources while enhancing the accuracy and reliability of SCAL data analysis. Additionally, we are expanding our capabilities in petrophysics, rock typing, SCAL upscaling, computer vision, and reservoir simulation, further advancing the precision and effectiveness of subsurface reservoir characterization, management, and supporting more informed decision-making.

Rotunda Scientific – Rotunda Scientific Technologies® LLC is dedicated to the fields of External Dosimetry, Radiation Detection, Radiation Protection and Spectroscopy. Founded in 2012 to serve the Dosimetry and Radiation Protection community, we supply innovative products and offer industry tailored services to fill voids that medium to large companies are not able or willing to address. We believe that listening to you and providing personalized service is the key to future partnerships and a long-term relationship. For this conference, we will be showcasing the GMS310 and GMS312 API Core Gamma Loggers.

Vinci Technologies/Floxlab - Vinci Technologies is an engineering company specializing in the design and manufacturing of highly specific instruments for rock and fluid analysis, as well as high-pressure metering pumps. Our product range includes rigs for measuring relative permeability and capillary pressure, conducting PVT studies, and performing triaxial rock compression tests. These versatile tools open up new market opportunities to address challenges in carbon sequestration and hydrogen storage.

Vindum Engineering Inc. - MANUFACTURER OF PRECISION HIGH PRESSURE PULSE-FREE PUMPS and VALVES

NEW VIPR Series Pumps: Large Volume Cylinder Pumps

- Easily upgrade to Continuous Pulse-Free Flow with 2 pumps
- Syringe Piston Design with Cylinder Wash Area
- CV Valves Standard
- VPware Software Included
- Gas or Liquids, including CO₂

VP Series Pumps: High Precision, Continuous Pulse-Free Metering Pumps

- Latest generation design: lower cost, higher performance
- Models up to 25,000 psi
- Ambient Temperature or High Temperature (up to 160C) Options
- Gas or Liquids, including CO₂

CV Valves: Constant-Volume, High-Pressure Valves

- Air activation
- High Temperature applications (up to 300C)
- Gas or Liquids, 2-Way and 3-Way Models

MV Hastelloy Valves & Fittings: Modular Manual Valve System

- Mountable, compact design saves space
- O-ring seals: replaceable, various seal materials
- Lower Cost Hastelloy Design
- In-stock for immediate delivery

Hastelloy Tubing: In stock for immediate delivery

Booth Layout

Coffee breaks will be served in the Exhibit area. Lunch will be a seated lunch downstairs.

Short Course Program

Digital Core Analysis: Pore-Scale Imaging, Modelling, and Deep Learning

August 26, 2024

Short Workshop: Digital Core Analysis: Pore-Scale Imaging, Modelling, and Deep Learning.	
Moderator: Ryan Armstrong	
8:30 – 8:40	Welcome and safety moment (Ryan Armstrong)
8:40 – 9:50 (10 min)	Course Introduction Presenter: Ryan Armstrong
8:50 – 9:40 (50 min)	Deep learning in pore-scale imaging and modelling Presenter: Masha Prodanovic
9:40 – 10:30 (50 min)	Deep learning in pore-scale imaging and modelling Presenter: Peyman Mostaghimi
10:30 – 10:50	Coffee Break Kindly Sponsored by: AMETEK Chandler Engineering
Moderator: Josephina Schembre-McCabe	
10:50 – 11:40 (50 min)	Industry 4.0 for Special Core Analysis: Overview, Research Trends, Opportunities, and Challenges. Presenter: Lesley James
11:40 – 12:30 (50 min)	Deep learning and Machine Learning for Core Analysis and Reservoir Characterization Presenter: Olivier Lopez
12:30 – 1:30	Lunch Kindly Sponsored by:

Technical Program

Monday, August 26, 2024

7:30 – 5:00	Registration Desk Open
1:30 – 3:00	<p>Session 1: Big Data Deep Learning and Machine Learning for Core Analysis</p> <p>Chairs: Naif Alqahtani and Olivier Lopez</p>
SCA1010	<p>Tree-Based Machine Learning Can Determine Lithofacies Properties of Reservoir Rocks- Gamal Oil field</p> <p>Hamada et al.</p>
SCA1036	<p>Federated Learning Test for Collaborative Machine Learning</p> <p>Chang et al.</p>
SCA1073	<p>Permeability inference from 3D grayscale images using deep learning: how large-scale dataset can contribute to model generalization.</p> <p>Youssef et al.</p>
3:00 - 3:30	<p>Coffee Break</p> <p>Kindly Sponsored by: AMETEK Chandler Engineering</p>
3:30- 5:00	<p>Session 2: Pore-Scale Imaging and Modelling I</p> <p>Chairs: Hyung Kwak and Souhail Youssef</p>
SCA1019	<p>Modeling Surface Roughness Effect in Porous Media: From Pore to Core Scale</p> <p>Li et al.</p>
SCA1030	<p>Variation of wettability across different lithotypes in a reservoir and its impact on Digital Rock Physics pore scale simulations</p> <p>Faisal et al.</p>
SCA1058	<p>Stress Dependency of Permeability and Porosity Using Micromechanics Digital Rock</p>

	Sun et al.
5:30 - 8:30	Opening Reception “Icebreaker Reception” Kindly Sponsored by: Chevron
Tuesday, August 27, 2024	
8:00 – 5:00	Registration Desk Open
8:30 - 9:30	Session 3: Core Analysis and Logging Interpretation Chairs: Jules Reed and Lesley James
SCA1060	Pre-operational drilling fluid evaluation of oil- and water-based drilling muds considering the impact on core analysis. A case study from the Upper Jurassic in the Northern North Sea Schleifer et al.
SCA1021	Evaluation of Residual Oil in the Wara, Mauddud, and Burgan Formations, Burgan Field, Kuwait Jonathan et al.
9:30 – 10:00	Exhibitor Presentations
10:00 - 10:30	Coffee Break Kindly Sponsored by: Math2Market GmbH
10:30 – 12:00	Session 4: MRI and NMR Chairs: Matthias Appel and Michael Dick
SCA1067	Fluid Quantification and Kerogen Assessment in Shales Using ¹³ C and ¹ H Magnetic Resonance Measurements Zamiri et al.
SCA1024	Discrete Inversion NMR (DI-NMR): An NMR data processing method for Accurate Fluid Typing and Saturation Determination

	Gao et al.
SCA1035	Determination of clay-bound water in non-conventional oil reservoirs via T1 NMR measurements. A case study for the Vaca Muerta formation. Domené1 et al.
12:00 - 1:00	Lunch Kindly Sponsored by:
1:00 – 1:30	Poster Presentations (SCA1016-SCA1061)
1:30 - 2:30	Coffee Break and Poster Session (SCA1016-SCA1061) Kindly Sponsored by: Math2Market GmbH
2:30 – 3:00	Exhibitor presentations
3:00 – 4:30	Session 5: Subsurface Storage Chairs: Stefano Pruno and Jon Burger
SCA01017	Measurement of CO2 Uptake Capacity in Source Rock Shales for GCS Chen et al.
SCA1057	Experimental determination of different saturation regions for underground geological CO2 storage Jenei et al.
SCA1022	Application of Analog Two-Phase Relative Permeability Data for Predicting the Full Cycle CO2/Brine Relative Permeability Curve Schembre-McCabe et al.
5:00 – 9:00 p.m.	Young Professional Event

	Kindly Sponsored by:
Wednesday, August 28, 2024	
8:15 – 5:00	Registration Desk Open
8:30 – 10:00	Session 6: Improved SCAL Techniques and Interpretation I Chairs: Christopher Jones and Matthieu Mascle
SCA1032	Relative Permeability Measurement Using Rapid In-Situ Saturation Measurement with MRI Zamiri et al.
SCA1077	Determination of Relative Permeabilities on Heterogeneous Samples Pairoys et al.
SCA1043	Investigation of Residual Oil Saturation at Different Capillary Number Regions through Surfactant-Polymer Flood Experiments Alabdumhusen et al.
10:00 - 10:30	Coffee Break Kindly Sponsored by:
10:30 – 12:00	Session 7: Displacement Mechanisms EOR/IOR I Chairs: Omid Karoussi and Xiaolong Yin
SCA1044	Investigating the Effect of Chemical Gradient in Polymer Flooding Alkandari et al.
SCA1031	Assessing the impact of dopants on electrokinetic rock properties as potential indicators for dopant induced wettability changes Halisch et al.
SCA1063	A Comprehensive Study on Nanoparticle-Surfactant Solutions for Foam-assisted Enhanced Oil Recovery: In-Depth Understanding via High Pressure Micromodel Visualization Experiments Machale et al.

12:00 - 1:00	Lunch Kindly Sponsored by:
1:00 – 2:00	Session 8: Improved SCAL Techniques and Interpretation II Chairs: David Potter and Cyril Caubut
SCA1011	A NOVEL APPROACH TO GAS CYCLING ENHANCED OIL RECOVERY (GCEOR) EVALUATION IN UNCONVENTIONAL POROUS MEDIA Thomas et al.
SCA1054	A Review of Primary Drainage Techniques Fernandes et al.
2:00 – 2:30	Poster Presentations (SCA1062-SCA1076)
2:30 - 3:30	Coffee Break and Poster Session (SCA1062- SCA1076) Kindly Sponsored by:
3:30 – 4:30	Session 9: Geothermal Chairs: Jon Burger and Matthias Halisch
SCA1014	A joint methodical case study for understanding severe formation clogging processes within a highly utilized geothermal reservoir in the Pannonian Basin of Hungary Njeru et al.
SCA1015	Thermal Conductivity: A Theoretically Simple, Yet Practically Challenging Experiment Gumpenberger et al.
6:30 – 9:30	Gala Dinner

	Kindly Sponsored by: iRock Technologies and Chevron
Thursday, August 29, 2024	
8:30 – 3:00	Registration Desk Open
8:30 - 10:00	Session 10: Displacement Mechanisms EOR/IOR II Chairs: Christopher Jones and Olga Vizika-Kavvadias
SCA1012	Foam Assisted Cyclic Solvent Injection in Heterogeneous Reservoirs Etemad et al.
SCA1028	An Experimental Investigation of Oil Recovery Mechanisms and Relative Permeability Curves obtained by Steady-State Versus Unsteady-State Displacement Alkhazmi et al.
SCA1042	Assessment of Magnetic Nanodroplets Propagation in Porous Media via Effluent Analysis Ahmadi et al.
10:00 - 10:30	Coffee Break Kindly Sponsored by :
10:30 – 12:00	Session 11: Pore-Scale Imaging and Modelling II Chairs: Franck Nono and Peyman Mostaghimi
SCA1026	A Versatile Workflow of Pore Geometry-Structure Rock Typing and Corey's Parameter-Based Relative Permeability Trend Modeling Akbar et al.
SCA1029	IMPROVE ON DUAL-ENERGY PROTOCOL FOR ROCK CHARACTERIZATION AND MONITORING OF POROSITY AND PHASE SATURATIONS DURING MULTIPHASE FLOW Vargas et al.
SCA1056	Digital Rocks Portal for Image Curation, Characterization, Visualization and Transport Simulation

	Turhan et al.
12:00 – 12:30	Business Meeting
12:30 - 1:30	Lunch Kindly Sponsored by: TBD
1:30 – 2:00	Poster Presentations (SCA1078-SCA1090)
2:00 - 3:00	Coffee Break and Poster Session (SCA1078-SCA1090) Kindly Sponsored by:
3:00 – 5:00	Session 12: Wettability Matthias Halisch and Mike Dick
SCA1027	The effect of wettability on the amount of adsorbed fluid and capillary condensation pressure in nanoporous materials Nguyen et al.
SCA1046	Potential wettability alteration-IOR study for pre-salt carbonate from experiments to field scale simulation Karoussi et al.
SCA1064	Characterizing Wettability Using ¹³ C Magnetic Resonance Relaxation Times Ansaribaranghar et al.
SCA1025	Pore scale investigation of dopant impact on wettability alteration Nono et al.
5:00	Closing Remarks

Alternate Orals

Alternation Orals	
SCA1083	Fast measurements of capillary pressure using the porous plate method: An alternative to MICP Lenormand et al.
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